

Original Article

Comparative Analysis on Dictatorship and Democratic System of Pakistan

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the key factors affecting political stability in Pakistan's democratic system, examine the impact of leadership during both democratic and dictatorial regimes, and recommend the most suitable system for ensuring long-term political stability in the country. By conducting a comparative analysis of democracy and dictatorship, this research explored which system better supports Pakistan's political stability. The study employed a qualitative research methodology, used historical and analytical approaches to investigate the leadership crisis and political developments in Pakistan. Primary and secondary sources were used to provide a comprehensive understanding of the issue. The findings revealed that both democracy and dictatorship have influenced political stability in different ways. While dictatorships offer short-term stability through centralized control, they often lead to political repression, corruption, dynastic politics, and weak accountability. In contrast, democracy despite being slow to deliver results supports sustainable development by promoting public participation, freedom of expression, strong institutions, and transparent governance. The study suggested that Pakistan could benefit from democracy if political awareness, voter turnout, and democratic institutions are improved. Recommendations include public literacy enhancement, awareness programs about democratic values, and governance accountability. Future research should use quantitative methods to assess public perceptions of democracy and dictatorship.

Keywords: Democratic Administrations, Accountability, Head count ratio, Cross-border terrorism, Political stability and public literacy

Introduction

Pakistan is a South Asian nation, formally known as the Islamic Republic of Pakistan. With a population of over 241.5 million, it is the fifth most populous country and, as of 2023, has the second-largest Muslim population. Karachi is the country's largest city and financial hub, while Islamabad serves as the capital. Pakistan faced democracy as well as dictatorship and they affect the state in both positive and negative ways. A dictatorship is a form of one-man rule in which the dictator is the ultimate leader and political freedom and participation are restricted. Because of its stringent governance and centralized legislature and executive branch, this system provides political stability. However, because of a lack of political awareness, it can also

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result in economic instability, dynastic politics, poor leadership, and political unrest. By comparing the two political systems, this study seeks to identify which is best for Pakistan's political stability.

Literature Review

Historical records demonstrate that a democracy promotes the interests of the general public, whereas a dictatorship serves the interests of a single individual. There are socioeconomic benefits and drawbacks to both regimes in society. Writers compared the socioeconomic performance of Pakistan under democratic and dictatorship (1947–2012) era. To analyze success, a variety of economic performance criteria were chosen for comparison, including the head count ratio (HCR), inflation and GDP growth, as well as literacy rates, life expectancy and population growth. This comparison is aided by statistical tests. The result from this article demonstrated that dictatorships are generally superior to democratic governments in every way. (Rasool, Hussain, Rashid & Srithilat, 2024). But my work demonstrates which factors are essential for democracy and how democracy will suit Pakistan.

The researchers study pinpointed the primary causes of Pakistan's high unemployment rate between 1977 and 2012, paying special attention to the part played by political structure. The sample period was divided into two regimes, democratic and dictatorial and the authors employed a dummy variable. The results demonstrate that both in the short and long run, investment growth reduces the unemployment rate. Only in the long term does real GDP growth lower the unemployment rate. Furthermore, their study's unexpected conclusion is that the unemployment rate in democracies is still much higher than in dictatorships. Important policy implications and suggestions for further research are also covered in that study (Ilyas & Khan, 2019).

It is stated that Pakistan has experienced both authoritarian and democratic regimes since gaining its independence. Even though the nation has been governed by multiple democratic administrations, Pakistani politicians have failed to provide the basic needs of life to the average citizenry. The lack of timely, free, and fair elections; the gap between the general public and the political elite, martial law, civil-military interactions, and ignorance are some of the major challenges to the achievement of democracy. Since its inception, Pakistan's political history has seen several transformations. Pakistan has experienced several brief periods of democracy in addition to four periods of martial law. Results: Under autocratic rule, growth was faster, and there was a significant difference in moveable debt, CPI inflation, and GDP growth rate. The anticipated results and conclusions of study and findings of the data analysis suggested that a significant development did not take place during the military-led era or that a significant development did occur during the dictatorship era (Siddiqi. & Saeed, 2021).

The writer goal of this study was to improve our comprehension of Pakistan's political leadership crisis as a recently formed nation. The paper's main goal was to identify the causes of the leadership crisis. Non-elected institutions like the military and civil bureaucracy were empowered as a result of political leadership rivalries and inefficiencies. According to that study, one of the main underlying factors contributing to the political instability of the nation was the crisis of political leadership. Because the political leadership was so preoccupied with power politics, they ceded control to the military and civil bureaucracy, which rose to prominence between 1948 and 1958 (Ullah, 2023). My study justifies that how leadership crisis Pakistan has been facing from post-independence to still in contemporary era.

Material and Methodology

The qualitative method has been applied for this research. Historical and analytical methods have all been used in the research process in order to move forward and reach a conclusion. It presents the research study's historical evidence on the leadership crisis. To gain a more comprehensive understanding various resources have been consulted, including literature reviews and secondary sources as well as primary sources, like journals, article, news article, official websites, books, report etc.

Comparative analysis on Dictatorship and Democratic System of Pakistan

Here is the brief comparison on democracy and dictatorship with factors that affect both.

Political stability

Political stability refers to a stable government or political system that maintains peace, order, and continuity over time. It is characterized by the rule of law, dependable institutions, and policies. Stable societies are less likely to experience significant political upheavals, civil unrest, or abrupt leadership changes. Social cohesion, economic expansion, and national development all depend on political stability. Consistent governance and policies facilitate long-term planning, investment, and prosperity for businesses and citizens. These are the followings factors that affect political stability in a state:

Sr.#	Democratic system	Dictatorship
1	Free and fair elections	Military control
2	Freedom of media	Suppression
3	Tolerance	Media control
4	Strong institutions	Propaganda
5	Economic stability	International pressure
6	Publication participation	Corruption

In democratic system, elections are crucial to electing their representatives. There are certain political parties that nominate their candidate and election commission of Pakistan conduct elections. If the election seen free and fair that is obviously sign of the political stability in the state for instance there was an in Pakistan first general election there was rigging in 1971 that caused drastic result with separation of East Pakistan. A democratic govt seen stable more than dictatorship because there is independence media perform their role but in dictatorship media is state controlled, censored and banned. There are more strengthened political institutions like parliament judiciary in democracy as compared to dictatorship. In democracy people actively participate in political processes but in contrast in dictatorship there is no public will. In dictatorship there is election dictator that came into power with the use of force, as General Pervez Musharraf overthrown the Nawaz Sharif government in 1999. Corruption is a factor that affects political stability in both democracy as well as in dictatorship. In dictatorship dictators face more international pressure to restore democracy and other aspects. dictatorship refers to short term stability with fast decision-making process, but short-term stability got on the cost of freedom, human rights etc. In democracy stability at start is slow but long lasting, in it there are strong institutions, and public participation.

Role of Leadership

Leadership is the main entity in every political system. Leaders led the nations to achieve their certain goals Quaid e Azam was well known enthusiastic leader who made a major work an independence of the Pakistan for Pakistan. But in 1948 after the death of Quaid e Azam left a gap of enthusiastic leaders in Pakistan. A leader is a decision-making body in both democratic and dictatorship .but the major difference in between are in dictatorship only one person made decisions without public will or demand. Dictators totally ignored public will and used force to control public in contrast inn democracy political leaders collectively participate in decision making process and listen public demands.in democracy political leaders are accountable and answerable to the public and parliament to the public. Dictatorship has strong and centralized leadership. A single person or a small group of people frequently hold all the power and make all the decisions in a dictatorship. Without the need for drawn out discussions or consultations, this can result in prompt and decisive action.

International relations

Democracy attracts more foreign respect, democratic countries like India, Pakistan got respect from other countries. International community provides aid, investment to restore and maintain democratic values. In Pakistan, political system has impacted the foreign relation of Pakistan with other countries. Since gaining independence in 1947, Pakistan and India have had a turbulent relationship, with conflicts stemming from dictatorships and wars. Pakistan's authoritarian style and emphasis on national security during dictatorships stoked animosity and mistrust. Both conflict and collaboration have existed in the relationship during

democratic governance. Important events include the 1972 Simla Agreement, the 1999 Lahore Declaration, the 2001 Agra Summit, the 2004 Composite Dialogue, the 2008 Mumbai attacks, and the 2019 Kartarpur Corridor. Even with these changes, tensions are still high because of things like Pakistan's alleged support for cross-border terrorism and Kashmir. In general, there has been tension and collaboration in the relationship between India and Pakistan (Khan, 2011).

Economic stability

Dictatorships can be useful for carrying out economic measures that support development and expansion. For instance, Pakistan's military rulers carried out a number of economic reforms in the 1960s and 1970s, which sped up the country's industrialization and expansion. Because decisions are made by a small group of people rather than a large and diverse population, dictatorships frequently offer a sense of stability and predictability. This can be especially alluring in a nation that has seen a lot of political unrest. Because they do not have to deal with interest groups, opposition parties, or frequent elections, dictatorships are typically more stable than democracies. In a nation with a history of political instability like Pakistan, this can be especially crucial. Because there is no need to reach an agreement or have drawn-out discussions, dictatorships can also be more effective at making decisions. This may enable policies and programs to be implemented more quickly. Since dictatorships are not subject to the demands of the general public or special interest groups, some contend that they can be more successful in fostering economic growth (Abbas, & Sultan, 2023).

Governance

Dictatorships are more stable than democracies because they do not have to deal with opposition parties, interest groups, or regular elections. This is especially important in countries like Pakistan, which have a history of political instability. A democracy has a higher level of political pluralism, which allows for the representation of different voices and interests. This can result in more inclusive and representative governance. Democratic systems typically provide greater protection for human rights such as free speech, assembly, and religion. This is especially important in a country like Pakistan, which has a history of human rights violations. Sectarian and ethnic tensions have often plagued Pakistan's democratic systems, with parties frequently aligning along these lines. This can cause polarization and conflict within society. Democracy encourages all citizens to participate in the political process, regardless of social or economic status. This can lead to a greater representation of diverse voices and perspectives in decision-making. Dictatorships frequently suppress individual rights. Such as free speech, religion, and association. This can lead to a society that is less tolerant and respectful of diversity (Jilani, 1998)

Accountability

Dictatorships, without checks and balances, are prone to corruption and nepotism. This can result in a concentration of wealth and power in the hands of a small elite at the expense of the rest of the population. Dictatorships lack the same level of accountability as democracies because there is no mechanism to hold leaders accountable for their actions. This can result in abuses of power, such as censorship, torture, and extrajudicial killings. While a dictatorship in Pakistan may have some potential benefits, such as strong leadership, stability, and economic development, these must be balanced against the significant disadvantages of political repression, corruption, and lack of accountability. Democracy remains the best system for promoting people's long-term well-being and protecting their fundamental rights and freedoms. Democracies have mechanisms for holding leaders accountable to the people, such as free and fair elections, independent media, and civil society. This can help to reduce corruption and abuse of power. While democracy can establish mechanisms for accountability and transparency, it cannot guarantee that leaders will not engage in corrupt behavior. Corruption remains a major concern in Pakistan's democratic system. In a democracy, leaders are held accountable to the people via free and fair elections. This can help make leaders more responsive to the needs and desires of the people they represent. Corruption can also occur in democracies, especially if

campaign finance laws are not strictly enforced or if politicians are more concerned with serving their own interests than the publics. In a dictatorship, leaders are not held accountable to the people through free and open elections. This can make it easier for leaders to prioritize their own interests over the best interests of the country (De Sousa, Hindess, & Larmour, 2012).

Democracy vs. dictatorship

The fact that both dictatorships and democracies have benefits and drawbacks should not be overlooked. In the end, the Pakistani people themselves should decide which type of government is best for their country. To select their preferred form of government and their leaders, they must be allowed to vote in a free and fair election. Along with working to improve and develop the nation and its citizens, the government should also be transparent and accountable. Although people may have differing views on this issue, democracy is generally a better option when weighed against the drawbacks of dictatorship and the advantages of free speech (Islam, 2001)

Conclusion

In conclusion, the political stability of Pakistan, a country in South Asia, has been impacted by both democracy and dictatorship. With centralized government, a legislative, and an executive branch, dictatorships—one-man governments with no political freedom offer stability. But they can also result in political upheaval, dynastic politics, economic instability, and ineffective leadership. Free and fair elections, military control, media freedom, tolerance, robust institutions, propaganda, economic stability, foreign pressure, and public involvement are all factors that impact political stability. In both democratic and autocratic regimes, leadership is essential. Whereas a single individual or group frequently controls all power under dictatorships, leaders in democracies are answerable to the people. Tensions and cooperation in Pakistan's ties with other nations may result from this. Although they frequently repress individual liberties and lack accountability, dictatorships can offer political pluralism and stability. Democracy fosters variety, lowers corruption, and encourages all citizens to participate. Depending on the choices of the populace, either democracy or dictatorship may be chosen, but democracy is typically preferable.

Recommendations

1. Public literacy and democracy are directly proportional to each other, more public literacy there are more chances of successful democratic government.
2. Government should introduce programs for public awareness about democratic norms and values and may focus on education department.
3. Government should make efforts to increase voter turnout rate. More public participation in elections caused more successful elections.
4. Government should learn about from past mistakes in democracy and dictatorship and avoid such mistakes in future.
5. Introducing such policies to strengthen democratic institutions like judiciary parliament

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